

Removal of turbidity and *E. coli* from surface water by electrocoagulation and study of its economic feasibility

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Abstract : Maximum turbidity removal of 98% is obtained in treatment of raw surface water by electrocoagulation (EC) system. As per World Health Organization (WHO) the permissible limit of turbidity of below 5 NTU can be achieved at a charge loading (CL) of 18 Coulomb/L at a pH value of 7.25. EC followed by plain sedimentation and filtration can remove of 19% of *E. coli* from raw water. Disinfection of filtered water is done by sodium hypochlorite solution (4% available chlorine). The complete (100%) removal of *E. coli* is achieved at a chlorine dose of 2.8 mg/L within 30 min of contact time. The treatment cost per liter of water estimated to be Rs. 0.072 per liter.

Keywords : Turbidity, electrocoagulation, *E. coli*, chlorination, disinfection.

I. Introduction

The scarcity of potable water is one of the major issues of the world. Low cost and efficient water treatment technology is inevitable for water industries, specially producing potable water. This technology should be sustainable. A sustainable system is socially acceptable, technologically feasible and economically viable. Any water treatment technology involves removal of turbidity, color, odor, heavy metals or metalloids nutrients, pesticides, pathogens etc. Suspended solids and colloids are mainly responsible for turbidity in surface water¹. Coagulation, flocculation, sedimentation and filtration are the basic common unit operations used to remove colloids effectively. The charge characteristics of colloid may differ depending on hydrophobic (clay) or hydrophilic colloids (proteins)². Low cost water treatment technology with small footprint has been reported efficient removal of turbidity, organic and pathogens^{3,4}. High quality water is the essential part

of modern life and this resource is becoming scarce very fast. In fact, the demand for water is still on the rise due to growing population. The centralized water treatment system demand huge funding with requirement of land, power, chemicals and maintenance staffs. Thus drinking water is becoming a costly commodity rapidly⁵.

Metal salts (alum, ferric salts etc.) are added as coagulant to neutralize surface charges which subsequently destabilized colloidal particles⁶⁻⁸. The process of coagulation is basically combined into surface charge neutralization of particles and floc formation defined as bridging the particles is called as flocculation⁹. Primary floc are formed by charge neutralization of unstabilized particles are also called coagulation floc and floc enlarged by bridging are sometimes termed as secondary flocs⁶. The coagulating agent, the pH of solution, the coagulant dosage, ionic strength, the concentration of solution and the nature of the organic compounds influenced the

efficacy of the process of flocculation¹⁰. Colloids are existing by particles over a size range of 1 nm (10^{-7} cm) to 0.1 nm (10^{-8} cm) and negatively charged. These particles do not settle out so easily and conventional physical treatment processes can not separate them rapidly¹¹. Conventional process demands determination of optimum pH, chemical dosages and maintaining of proper alkalinity for effective removal of turbidity. The process generates large amount of sludges¹².

EC is a process by which anodic material is corroded out into raw water by application of external DC power source¹³. This system can be used as promising sustainable technology to treat surface water at urban, semi urban areas as well rural drinking water supply systems¹⁴. The EC system fulfills the requirement of easiness of operation, maintain quality and quantity of water production and low sludge production for per unit of volume treated. The functionality of EC system fulfills automatic pH adjustment and alkalinity requirement¹⁵.

During electrocoagulation anode (typically aluminum or iron) is corroded out and supplementary electrolytic reactions take place which depend on the solution chemistry. The basic chemical reactions that take place at the aluminum electrodes during electrocoagulation are presented below¹⁶.

It is reported that electrocoagulated sludge tends to settle quick compared to chemical coagulation. In association with above electrode reactions following

reactions also take place with aluminum as an anode¹⁷.

With iron as anodic material, after anodic dissolution, subsequent reactions take place with dissolved oxygen and ferric hydroxide is formed¹⁸.

In most of the studies EC has been applied to wastewater treatment^{19,20}. Very less studies are reported for treat surface water for drinking purpose. In this work EC process with aluminum electrode as anode material and solar energy as power source has been used to remove turbidity and *E. coli* from surface water and an economic feasibility of the process has been studied.

II. Materials and methods

Batch experiments were conducted with 1500 mL active volume of surface water samples. The surface water samples were collected from River Ganga near Botanical Garden Ghat, Howrah, West Bengal, India. The average characteristics of collected surface water are presented in Table 1. Solar Panel (Aplab India Limited) mounted on the roof top of the Environmental Engineering Laboratory, IEST, Shibpur and the required current has been set by the regulator. For dosing of coagulant, aluminium plates were used as anode and cathode with monopolar electrode configuration. The spacing between the electrodes was maintained at 5 mm with an active electrode area of 80 cm² is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of experimental set-up for electrocoagulation system.

The batch electrocoagulation experiments were carried out in the laboratory in 2 litres capacity borosil glass jar over different time intervals of EC process and initial pH of solution was 7.03. That was measured by a pH meter (WTW, Germany). Turbidity of water was measured with a Nephelometer (Systronics India Ltd., Analog, 131). The raw water quality parameters (Table 1) are measured as laid down in American Public Health Association (APHA) Standard Methods (1995)²¹.

Table 1. The characteristics of raw water

Parameter	Range	Unit
pH	7.0–7.5	–
Turbidity	120–230	(NTU)
Hardness	140–180	(mg/L as CaCO ₃)
Alkalinity	180–220	(mg/L as CaCO ₃)
MPN	109900–462000	(Nos./100 ml)

A preferred amount of current was passing through the solution for specified period and solution was stirred in a jar test apparatus for 30 s flash mixing followed by 20 min slow mixing for floc formation. The polished water collected by settling the floc for 30 min followed by sand filtration. A lesser portion (100 ml approx.) of the content was withdrawn and filtered with 12° sand filter and turbidity was then measured.

To find the chlorine dose for disinfection, experiments were conducted to find the break point chlorination. The chlorine dose was used with commercial NaOCl solution of 4% chlorine available. The water was filtered and different amount of chlorine was dosed. The residual chlorine was measured to find the break point chlorination²¹.

A. Cost analysis

With water scarcity and pressure to meet drinking water requirements the water industries are in immense responsibility to deliver affordable good quality and reliable water supply throughout the year²². Fig. 2 shows the flow diagram of EC system and associated cost components.

(1) Fixed costs

- (a) Solar panel (for 10 yrs. lifespan) = Rs. 70,000
- (b) Experimental setup (for 10 yrs. lifespan) = Rs. 4,502
- (c) Storage tank (for 1500 lit capacity) = Rs.14, 835.

Fig.2. Flow diagram for electrocoagulation system with cost components.

Total fixed cost = Rs. 89,337

(2) Variable costs

(a) Rechargeable battery. Rs. 2500/yr. × 10 yrs.
= Rs. 25,000

(b) Electrode consumption. Rs. 88.20/yr. × 10 yrs.
= Rs. 882

(c) Disinfectant. Rs. 5518.8/yr. × 10 yrs.
= Rs. 55,188.

(d) Labour* (@ Rs. 359/cleaning, twice in a month) Rs. 359 × 2 × 12/yr. × 10 yrs. = Rs. 86,160

*Minimum wages for central sphere for Area C from Ministry of Labour Employment published at Gazette notified on 01.04.2017.

Total variable cost = Rs. 167,230

III. Results and discussion

A. Turbidity removal and disinfection

The test result shows that (Fig. 3) after 18 coulomb/L of charge density, turbidity becomes less than 5 NTU. With an operating current of 0.15 amp this value is achieved in 120 s of electrocoagulation. The test result suggests that the advantage during the process of EC followed by sedimentation achieved 19% of *E. coli* removal. Disinfection of filtered water by a chlorine dose of 2.8 mg/L achieved 100% removal within 30 min of contact time.

Fig. 3. Effect of charge density on turbidity removal.

B. Effect of pH on turbidity removal

It is clear that from Fig. 4 during the electrocoagulation process the maximum turbidity removal below 5 NTU was obtained at a pH value of 7.25. It is also clear that the pH did not change significantly during the period of electrocoagulation and remains within the value (6.5–8.5) stipulated in the drinking water standard. Thus, EC acts as buffer during turbidity removal process.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on turbidity removal.

C. Cost benefit analysis

The cost benefit analysis of surface water treatment by electrocoagulation was done for 10 years of life span of the solar panel. The chemical cost of the disinfectant was considered at a break point chlorination dose of 2.8 mg/L. Now for calculation of the case of complex interest purpose “Amortization factor (*a*)” was introduced in calculation. It is a fixed repayment schedule for paying off debt paying in regular installment over a period of time²³.

$$\text{Amortization factor } (a) = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)-1}$$

where, *i* = rate of interests (10%) (RBI Annual Policy statement 2017-2018, April 2017) and *n* = time period (10 yrs.).

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$$\text{Amortization factor } (a) = \frac{0.1 \times (1+0.1)^{10}}{(1+0.1)^{10}-1} = 0.163$$

Total cost after 10 yrs. to apply complex interest
= Capital cost $\times (1+a) = 167,230 \times (1+0.163) =$
Rs. 194,488.49

Total fixed cost in 10 yrs. = Rs. 89,337

Net cost for all setup for drinking water supply =
(194,488.49 + 89,337) = Rs. 283,825.49

The volume of water will be treated for 10 yrs.
= (10 yrs. \times 365 days/yr. \times 1.5 L/2 min \times 1440 min/
day) = 3,942,000 L.

(A single unit can treat 1080 liter/day),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of treatment} &= \frac{283,825.49}{3,942,000} = \text{Rs. } 0.072/\text{L} \\ &= \text{Paise } 7.2/\text{L} \end{aligned}$$

Personal communication with the personnel of Padmapukur water treatment plant, Howrah, West Bengal confirms that due to price hike current surface water treatment cost per liter is about 15 paise.

IV. Conclusion

In this study raw Ganga water has been treated by EC process taking solar energy as the driving source. The system can bring down turbidity from 120 NTU to below 5 NTU with a charge loading of 18 Coulomb/L at the rate of 0.15 amp current and 120 s of operating time. The maximum turbidity removal was obtained at a pH of 7.25. The added advantage of the EC process is that it does not require alkalinity adjustment and pH remains stable within the limit of drinking water standard. EC followed by sedimentation achieved 19% of *E. coli* removal. Disinfection of filter water by a chlorine dose of 2.8 mg/L achieved 100% removal of *E. coli* within 30 min of contact time. The treatment cost per liter of water is estimated to be Rs. 0.072 per liter. This system can be effectively installed in small communities even in

municipality areas where untreated raw surface water is supplied.

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